

Putting Stock in Fleeting Temporal Affirmations

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Abstract

In an era of the pervasiveness of social media its participants inevitably receive affirmations of their achievements, big and small and other broadcasted positive outcomes, and feel buoyed by the sense of acclamation. However, commendations are invariably short-lived. To stay in the feel-good space one must continue to be reinforced with positive affirmations. In the context of one's flailing capacities or simply because of being crowded out by competing messages of good outcomes from others, affirmations from one's social media contacts and followers may soon dry up. While affirmations understandably add to the aura of distinction, regrettably they do not always associate the spark of fine quality with ways God made it possible to exceed native potential. When positive credits are no longer forthcoming, and worse, if disparagement begins to set in, depression invariably rises.

Introduction

There is always sadness in the community among family and friends when one of them lapses into chronic depression, especially with suicidal tendencies. Anxiety and depression are the two most prevalent mental health problems across the world today. Unfortunately, this disorder is trending upward, particularly among younger people who appear disillusioned with what life has to offer. The incidence of this morbidity has been made worse with the Covid 19 pandemic and is being evidenced in several countries with people feeling sadly depressed by their prospects. A singular reason for this dependency seems to be that positive outcomes do not appear to be forthcoming thus leading to these people acquiring a bleak view of life. An early study by Hidaka (2012) identified that a major cause of depression is having been groomed in environments that continually applauded them

(including for trivial achievements), these despairing folk have not been sufficiently exposed to rebuffs and rejection. They unwittingly have cultivated a belief of entitlement to receiving kudos and when denied the credit, in whatever shape or form, they are sometimes overcome with extreme disillusionment that puts them on a dangerous slippery slope.

In an era where social media seems to consume significant time and attention, participants are regularly bombarded by messages of accomplishments of whom they know or know about, provoking responses in the form of likes and congratulatory emojis. Inevitably an urge is created among social media partakers to emulate the feats of their peers and unconsciously expect the same or more affirmative responses. The absence of such felicitations predictably creates dissonance of their lifestyle attributes including their conduct, performance and self-esteem leading many a time to gross disenchantment. Such disillusionment has the potential to trigger withdrawal and evoke dark thoughts. Facebook and Google, the leading purveyors of social media do not appear to care about the harmful effects of the self-imposed shame of many of their members much of which is caused by too much affirmation from algorithmically controlled social media, that encourages superficial and mostly positive portrayals of the lives of its users.

Rather Facebook and Google, keen to have their users respond in ways that suit their commercial interests, palpably encourage participation in this zero-sum game. Through algorithms, social media companies curate information and decide what their users see. They amplify some players and mute others in mostly non-transparent ways. The documentary-drama hybrid *The Social Dilemma* exposes the dangerous human impact of networking, with tech experts sounding the alarm about their creations. The film shows how social media behemoths track social media players and vary algorithms, themes, background information and music to mesmerise and string their users to continually stay on track and get continued exposure to the ‘feats’ of their peers to the extent that drives their urge to imitate. Gore Vidal (1925–2012), the American writer and public intellectual known for his epigrammatic wit, once said “Whenever a friend succeeds, a little something in me dies”. Small wonder then why so many Facebook and other social media chronic users are in inexorable mental decline because they struggle to emulate their peers. And if social media participants have been nurtured in the belief of entitlement the absence of commendations can often result in severe anxiety disorder and depression.

1. Affirmations Lift Spirits

Affirmation at its most elemental level recognises the affirmed for what they are before proceeding to acknowledge to what value they can contribute either for themselves or to others or society. It is a form of recognition that immediately gives a sense of comfort and security because of the emotion of being felt as special and important. Notably, the act of affirmation makes the affirmed feel that they have enough of the particular attribute and are free from being devalued. This is especially important in testing times when we feel depressed trapped by mistakes and consequently discouraged to live with freedom. Cohen and Sherman (2014) in their study of social-psychological intervention assert that affirmations can have longer benefits when they touch off a cycle of adaptive potential, a positive feedback loop between the self-system and the social system that propagates adaptive outcomes over time. The elixir-type effect of affirmations is hardly surprising since affirmations invariably express affection through spoken praise/appreciation and acts of service and care. If one can rely on Christian ethical reflection as a tool for addressing challenges of social engagement, Ps 16: 24 makes the concept of affirmation very palpable: “Pleasant words are a honeycomb, sweet to the soul and healing to the bones.” And Prov 17:22 “A joyful heart is a good medicine, but a crushed spirit dries up the bones.”

2. When Affirmations Dry Up

Wanting to maintain a scorecard of our successes is by itself not a bad thing. Having others “affirm” our achievements and/or self-congratulate ourselves for positive outcomes arising from our efforts inevitably encourages us to persevere to better the positive results or at least sustain them. It is not unnatural for recipients of affirmations to feel buoyed and keep seeking even more credits. The unfortunate character of human affirmations is that they are short-lived and constantly need to be reinforced. There is no guarantee that regular affirmations of the same intensity or with similarly expressed adulation will follow performances or situations that beg acclaim especially if performance is considered to have dropped because of flailing capacities or improved comparative performances by contemporaries.

Often the lack of forthcoming credit results in the neural network going into recess and invariably causing the recipient depression. There is no gainsaying that to expect to achieve continuous top billing is living in a fool's paradise, yet a lot of the time it is extremely difficult for those who have

enjoyed time in the limelight to acknowledge that they are an "also-ran"! Disappointment is a natural human trait that arises when outcomes move away from expectations. The concern is that if for some reason forthcoming performances or situations are not as eventful or noteworthy, and affirmations dry up or worse if performance and/or situations bring on detractions, the consequent drought of kudos may provoke prolonged bouts of heightened anxiety and depression.

3. Sustaining Affirmations

It is not commonly recognised that the Beatitudes expressed by Jesus (Matthew 6: 1-12) are an exemplar of affirmations that hold their truth permanently and never lose the credit bestowed on the recipients. In Matthew's narration, people from far and wide followed Jesus hoping to hear him teach and be cured of their discomfiture. They came with various uncomfortable dispositions and included those who felt low in spirit, those who had long-term suffering, those who were mourning and grieving, those who suffered injustice, and those who were being persecuted for being righteous. Jesus called these faithful to himself by the side of a mountain and began to engage with their infirmities Jesus meant to credit them for believing in him and affirmed that each of them was "blessed" (living with God) for the privilege of a disposition which allowed them to engage with goodness (Kingdom of God), i.e. himself. The affirmations expressed by Jesus appear to use logical paradox to good effect by giving credit to the infirmities of his followers as if they should be celebrating their poor disposition. Supreme Teacher as he is, Jesus was well aware, as contemporary research studies have now shown, that positive affirmations can overcome inherent negative qualities of mind and character. Through his affirmations, Jesus intended to get his followers, seeking a cure for their disorders, to feel " happy" that their condition is to be celebrated always and never to be grieved because the Lord assured them that they were living with God (just as they would be in heaven).

Jesus further reiterates his affirmation of his disciples for their worth and virtuousness by referring to them as the "salt of the earth" and the "light of the world" (Mt 5:13-16). Back then salt was highly prized as a preservative of food – so precious that it was used as money. Salt is a natural compound of Sodium (Na) and Chloride (Cl). In its pristine form salt can never go bad in terms of losing its saltiness, flavour or preservative character. However, when mixed with other elements like iodine (to assist health improvement),

salt can get bad if the elements it is mixed with get corrupted. Jesus' reference to the paradox of salt losing its saltiness is to highlight to his followers the danger of being mixed with elements that could potentially go bad and corrupt their pristine character, thus meeting the fate of salt being trampled over when it has lost its saltiness. On the other hand, Jesus affirms his faithful, being the light of the world, that their glow can never be hidden under a table but rather, as followers of the Lord, be like a city built on top of the hill for all to behold and emulate.

4. Misconstrued Affirmations

Affirmations may sometimes not be received in the spirit in which they were delivered because of different interpretations of the expression of the affirmation. Instead of the affirmation buoying the recipient these misconstrued commendations can create confusion and even dissonance.

However, even if affirmations have achieved their specific purpose with the intended recipients, it is not uncommon to find that they have drawn contested representation when interpreted by others despite being expressed contextually in the most precise and compelling way. The impact of affirmations can sometimes be construed differently from its desired purpose by non-recipients not fully aware of the emotion carrying the affirmation. Casting aspersions on the true intention of the affirmation thus creating doubt in the mind of the recipient that the commendation was tongue in cheek, misdirected or simply sarcastic. Affirmations that come across this way are likely to break the spirit of the recipient and would never come out of the mouth of Jesus. One of the chief missions of Jesus was teaching and while innuendo was a regular character of his parables but never was intended to mock or to be ironic. Vested interests however still reconstructed the real meaning of his affirmations to suit their immediate agendas.

Two of Jesus' most acclaimed affirmations, one to Peter his apostle, when Jesus ordained him to build his church (Matthew 16:18) and the other to the thief crucified by Jesus' side that he would have the criminal joined in Paradise on the next day (Luke 23:43), while not showing any evidence in the bible of not being understood by the two men respectively, have historically evoked controversies despite being expressed with exactitude and persuasiveness.

The acclamation of Peter that has far-reaching implications for the establishment of the Church and its history is the one Jesus bestowed on Peter: "And I tell you that you are Peter, and on this rock, I will build My

church, and the gates of Hades will not prevail against” (Mt 16:18). To Peter and those around Jesus, this honour was well understood. Taken in the literal sense, Peter appears to have eminently acquitted himself in converting the Jews and Gentiles to the first Christians and also for taking Christianity far and wide. Further, the mantle that Peter was thus given by Jesus did not appear to carry any hierarchical implications among Jesus' apostles because we learn from scripture that at various other times, Jesus sought the views of other apostles including James and Paul ahead of Peter. Nonetheless, the Church (*Ecclesias* in Greek means syndication of like-minded people) was made the responsibility of Peter with a promise from Jesus that such an institution would be built on a firm foundation i.e., on *rock* (*in the languages of both Syriac- Aramaic and Greek, Cephas/Petro which translate as Peter are akin to Cephassa /Petra*) and would never be assailed by any type of ravages. Despite the metaphor of the affirmation being well understood by Peter and those around him, controversy, sometimes even violence has raged over centuries as to the correct meaning of what Jesus meant by “and on this rock I will build my church.” It is argued whether Jesus referred to Peter as the rock or whether his faith in Jesus and his confession that he had made hitherto this affirmation was the rock or whether it was Jesus himself that is being referred to as the rock.

When hanging from the cross, Jesus' response to the second criminal's admonishment to the first one's insults (to Jesus), drew the following commendation from Jesus: “Truly I tell you, today you will be with Me in Paradise.” (Lk 23:43). Jesus was wont to emphasise the authority of his affirmation with the prefix “truly” whenever his message was profound with special significance. Interestingly, Jesus uses the term “truly” seventy-six times in the New Testament and no one else other than Jesus ever says it. Over centuries much controversy has been broiled among biblical scholars regarding the placement of the comma before or after “today.” Depending on the comma placement, the assertion would suggest that the acclaim is being made today or that Jesus had affirmed the criminal joining his spirit today in paradise. The debate is understandable because Christian belief is that Jesus rose from the dead only on the third day and all that while his body lay in the tomb. The controversy over the appropriate punctuation highlights the sensitivity of the differences in expressive meaning in conveying the full import of the affirmation.

If interpretations of such diverse nature can be construed as *abiding affirmations* by one who undoubtedly expressed his thoughts in the most

precise and compelling way for understanding and effect, it can be imagined how fraught with danger well-intended affirmations made by mortals could easily be construed very differently from what they are meant to convey.

5. Compelling Affirmations

Current medical literature has established that affirmation is noted to have a positive impact on the neural network through the generation of positive dopamine hormones. Dopamine, a mood elevator, is known to have a significant effect in improving the quality of life, mental health and HIV outcomes. Much about anxiety disorders and depression is still unknown and research on improving the level of enzymes that energise the brain is still underway. Kinnear et al. (2009) study on attributions and affirmations for overcoming anxiety and depression identified that most recovered patients considered “they were bigger and better than their affliction”. Recovered patients claimed the strong affirmation that “they were not crazy” was significant in their recovery process. Ironically, this same cohort spread over eclectic religious persuasions, on aggregate scored low on reliance on spirituality and belief that God was instrumental in their recovery. It is important to remember however that expecting praise as an entitlement is a vitiating factor in the recovery from depression because most often the entitlement belief is an expectation of a contingent reward as opposed to being satisfied with the *intrinsic* reward of the enjoyment of doing the activity for its own sake. Any effort that gives intrinsic credit reflects good work. Compromising intrinsic credit risks forgetting the Lord’s timeless affirmation: “You are precious and honoured in my sight” (Isa 43:4). We being God’s handiwork, were created in Christ Jesus to do good works, which God prepared in advance for us to do (Eph 2:10). Contingent reward *reduces* the appeal of intrinsic reward and searches for exogenous affirmation which may or may not be forthcoming. The false positive of contingent affirmation is vindicated in Steele’s (1988) theory of psychology behind affirmation that human beings have a fundamental motivation to maintain their self-integrity, or their natural perception of themselves as being good, virtuous, and capable of controlling the outcome of important events. While some people may appear to have been denied life’s favoured outcomes, a conviction that divine empathy for their struggles will eventually redeem their stress is borne out in the affirmation: “The last will be first, and the first last” (Mt 20:16).

Conclusion

The unfortunate character of human commendations is that they are short-lived and constantly need to be reinforced, often with reduced immediate impact or diminishing utility, especially in the context of flailing capacities or demonstrated improved performance by others. Further affirmations may get lost in translation because they are not accepted as intended. Nonetheless, it is natural for recipients of affirmations if positively received to feel buoyed and keep seeking even more credits. Affirmations naturally add to the aura of brilliance. Regrettably, not always does one ascribe the spark of brilliance to ways God made it possible to exceed our native potential. When positive credits are no longer forthcoming, and worse if detraction begins to set in, depression will inevitably arise. Putting stock therefore in fleeting temporal affirmations is treading on a slippery slope. Without trivialising the challenges of nurturing the mental health of those besieged with this condition of not being considered outstanding, it may be useful to consider a mitigating intervention of recalling the words of Apostle Paul in 2 Cor 3:5 “Not that we are competent of ourselves to claim anything as coming from us; our competence is from God”. In Isa 43:4 God promises all of humanity that we are precious and honoured in his sight and does not require us to keep bettering our performances to stay in his abiding love. We need to recognise the strength and vitality in the way we go about fulfilling our objectives is not our own but rather God’s omniscience on display in our strengths and weaknesses.

Sufferers of anxiety disorder and depression commonly consider the major assertion that assisted them in turning the corner as they were bigger than their disease. This belief is rooted in the assertion of Isaiah 64.8 “Yet you, Lord, are our Father. We are the clay, you are the potter; we are all the work of your hand” and should be a major consideration of sufferers of anxiety disorder and depression that they cannot be belittled by their disease. Reliance on scriptural tenets begs the question of why compulsive social media participants should put their limbic systems in peril by persistently relying on affirmations to be propped up. Unambiguous and sufficient defence against fickle temporal affirmations is assured by the abiding love of God (John 3:16) who made us fearfully and wonderfully (Psalm 139) and who sees Himself in us (Gen 1:27).

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